

ANALYSIS METHOD OF TURN – TAKING SIGNALS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS’ SPEAKING SKILL

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ABSTRACT

As an international language, English has been remarked with many changes, notably the changes in the movement towards the teaching of English. Teaching and learning English in Vietnam is not excluded from the international trend as Vietnam is broadening and improving the relationship and co – operation with other countries in many fields of life Teaching a foreign language refers to teaching different aspects, in which speaking is of the great importance. Conversation analysis is the study of talk in interaction and mostly characterised by turn-taking. Turn-taking is one of the most basic mechanisms in conversaion and its main feature is to promote and maintain talk. Turn - taking varies between cultures and languages; consequently, it is often confused and difficult for learners to take and give turns in the target language due to limited background knowledge and language competence. Therefore, this writing will aim at studying turn-taking signals and giving analysis of certain turn-taking signals in conversations thoroughly both in theory and practice with the hope to improve students’ communication skill in English as well as their proficiency in general.

Keywords: turn – taking, conversation, English, speaking skill, analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conversation analysis is the study of talk in interaction and mostly characterised by turn-taking. Turn-taking is one of the most basic mechanisms in conversaion and its main feature is to promote and maintain talk. However, it is often confused and difficult for learners to take and give turns in the target language due to limited background knowledge and language competence. Therefore, this writing will aim at studying turn-taking signals and giving analysis of certain turn-taking signals in conversations.

2 TURN-TAKING AND TURN-TAKING SIGNALS

2.1 Definition of turn and turn-taking

According to Levinson, S.C. (1983), “**a turn** is a time during which a single participant speaks, within a typical, orderly arrangement in which participants speak with minimal overlap and gap between them”.

The term “**turn-taking**” includes how to take the floor without interrupting, how to keep the floor and how to pass the floor. Coulthard (1985) considered “**turn-taking** as one of the basic facts of conversation: speakers and listeners change their roles in order to begin their speech”. Cook, G. (1989) stated that “conversation involves **turn-taking** and that the end of one speaker’s turn and

the beginning of the next's frequently latch onto each other with almost perfect precision and split-second timing".

More specially, Yule, G. (1996) gives a very true and simple description of **turn** and **turn-taking** system "**Floor** is seen as the right to speak. Having control of this floor at any time is called a **turn**. In any situation where control is not fixed in advance, anyone can attempt to get action. This is called **turn-taking**. **Turn-taking** operates in accordance with a local management system that is conventionally known by members of a social group. The local management system is essentially a set of conventions for getting turns, keeping them or giving them away. This system is needed most at those points where there is a possible change in who has the turn. Any possible change-of-turn point is called a **Transition Relevance Place (TRP)**".

In my opinion, turn-taking is understood as the communication behavior of alternating messages from one person to the other. It refers to the distribution of turns among participants in a conversation. Turn taking mechanism is the way in which speakers hold or pass the floor, it varies between cultures and languages and it is the most obvious characteristics of conversation.

2.2 Rules of turn-taking

Sacks, Schegloff and Jefferson proposed two rules of operating turns which Levinson modified later as follows:

"Rule 1: applies initially at the first TRP of any turn:

- (a) If the current speaker selects the next speaker in current turn, then current speaker must stop speaking and the next speaker must speak next, transition occurring at the first TRP after next speaker selection.
- (b) If the current speaker does not select the next speaker, then any other party may self-select, first speaker gaining rights to the next turn.
- (c) If the current speaker has not selected the next speaker, and no other party self-selects, then current speaker may (but need not) continue.

In other words, this rule governs the turn-taking system or explains how turns are operated among participants in a conversation. The rule includes three main points: Current Speaker selects Next Speaker; Next Speaker Self-selects as Next; or Current Speaker Continues.

Rule 2: applies at all subsequent TRPs:

When rule 1(c) has been applied by current speaker, then at the next TRP rules 1 (a) and (c) apply; and recursively at the next TRP, until speaker change is effected."

2.3 Signals in turn-taking

In ordinary conversation, participants always use signals to inform that their turn is about to end with verbal and non-verbal cues. People often take turns during the conversation when they realise the signals indicating that they are selected or nominated by the current speaker and sometimes when no one is selected, they will self-select. Following are some basic cues of turn-taking:

Questions and tag-questions:

In conversation, when one party raises a question, it will be a cue for the other realises and gives response. For example:

E.g. 1: A: Nice day, isn't it?

B: Sure.

E.g.2. A: Where are you from?

B: Toronto, Canada.

Complete sentence:

It is a quite frequent thing that most turns end in a complete sentence or complete information, thus, they signal the end of a turn. For example:

A: How long have you been in this city?

B: **About two years**

A: **So you've been here longer than me**

B: When did you come?

Adjacency pairs:

One of the most noticeable things about conversation is that certain classes of utterances conventionally come in pairs called the adjacency pairs; for example, questions and answers, greetings and return greetings etc. Thus, adjacency pairs are the basic structural units in conversations, they are used for opening and closing conversations. They occur when the utterance of one speaker makes a particular kind of response very likely. (Hoang Van Van, 2006). For example:

E.g.1 A: Good morning!

B: Good morning!

E.g.2 A: Bye. See you again

B: Bye. See you.

E.g.3 A: How are you?

B: Fine, thanks. And you?

A: I'm so so. Thanks.

Special phrases:

Such phrases as "or something like that", "you know", "I don't know" are also very effective in signaling a turn. For example:

E.g.1. Customer: I would like to have tomato soup or something like that.

Waiter: OK, I'll be right back.

E.g.2. A: I've registered myself to the Orienteering Club, you know.

B: Really?

Back channels responses:

To inform the speaker that one do not take his turn, there are linguistic means called **back channels** responses such as hmm, ah-ha, mmm, er For example:

Caller: If you use your long distance service a lot, then you'll

Mary: uh-uh

Caller: be interested in the discount I'm talking about because

Mary: Yeah

Caller: it can only save you money to switch to a cheaper service

Mary: Mmm (George Yule, p.75)

Using **back channels responses** in the case of Mary indicates to the caller that his/her message is being received and that the listener is following, not objecting to what the caller is saying. In some cases, the absence of **back channels** may lead to silence and responses may be interpreted as a way of disagreement.

Apart from the above linguistic signals, the use of non-linguistic ones which make turn-taking efficient. Following are brief descriptions of each cue:

Intonation and volume

Intonation is one of the most important signals that speakers often pay much attention to in order to take turns or hold turns. It refers to the rise and fall of the pitch of the voice in spoken language, in other words, intonation is "the linguistic use of pitch in utterances".

English intonation is composed of some separate systems: tone which refers to pitch movements, prominence, key and termination; of which tone is considered to contribute to a wide range of different meanings. There is a distinction between primary and secondary tones. Primary tones are the basic and contrastive pitch movement on the tonic curve which moves up (rise), or moves down (fall) or combines a movement of down and then up (fall-rises). Secondary tones are the finer distinctions of the primary tones.

- **Falls:** A fall indicates the speaker's dominance in knowing and telling someone what to do and in expressing their own feelings, or it may indicate the completeness of information of an utterance.
- **Rises:** A rise indicates the speaker's deference to addressee's knowledge, their right to decide and their feelings or it may indicate incomplete information before a fall or minor information after a fall.
- **Fall-rises:** A falling-rising tone before a fall indicates theme highlighting, after a fall or independently it indicates an implication, an unspoken message that calls for attention.

Pause and silence

The use of pause and silence in conversation can be interpreted as the cues to pass or insist a turn. According to Yule, G. (1996), "very short pauses are simply hesitations, but longer pauses become silences". If one speaker actually turns over the floor to another and the other does not speak, then the silence is attributed to the second speaker and becomes significant.

Linguists divide silent pauses into two types: switching pause and hesitation pause. **Switching pause** is silence between turns; it is called utterance-final pause or end-of-turn pause. **Hesitation pause** is conversational silence that occurs within a turn. It is also called utterance-internal pause or in-turn pause.

Following is the example of switching pause:

Jan: Dave, I'm going to the store.

[2 seconds]

Jan: Dave?

[2 seconds]

Jan: Dave – Is something wrong?

Dave: What? What's wrong?

Jan: Never mind.

(George Yule, p73)

Overlap

Overlap is one way of signaling a desire to take a turn in a conversation, when a listener begins speaking before the first speaker completely finishes his turn. Overlaps can be seen as direct interruptions; sometimes they occur at a point in the conversation where a speaker has just completed a thought – even when the current speaker intends to continue. They may also indicate that the listener believes he or she understands the gist of the first speaker's message and can now begin his or her conversational turn. Additionally, overlaps also indicate that a person is responding to what was being said when the overlap started. Thus, an overlap can also signal to what the next statement refers. As a result, overlaps have the effect of keeping conversational turns relatively short which also limits the number of new ideas per turn. When fewer new ideas are introduced per turn, the flow of conversation may be easier to follow and remember. However, in other cases where there is overlap between turns, it has some particular significance signaling annoyance, urgency or excitement or a desire to correct what is being said.

Overlaps may be interpreted differently in different contexts and may take different functions. They show a first difficult conversation with an unfamiliar person, or an expression of solidarity or closeness, especially among younger speakers. In some cases, overlap communicates competition or discussion. If the expectation is that only one person speaks at a time then the overlap can be a serious problem.

E.g. A: Hello! I'm interested in the house for rent. Where exactly is it?

B: It is in the city centre, next to Rex Cinema. But...

A: //How many bedrooms are there?//

B: Four, but the house...

A: //How many bathrooms are there?//

B: There are two, I'm sorry....

A: //What..?//

B: I'm sorry, the house is not available now.

A: Oh thank you.

“//..... //” indicates that speaker B is trying to get the turn while speaker A still talking.

Gestures, body movement and eye contact

In ordinary conversation, gestures, the movement of the body especially eye contact play an important and effective role in getting into or out of the conversation. They help the listeners much in realizing their turns and also draw the listeners attention to the conversation.

In conclusion, there are a number of signals of turn-taking in conversation, both linguistic and non-linguistic ones which are significant and effective in keeping the conversation smooth and natural.

3 ANALYSIS OF SOME TURN-TAKING SIGNALS FROM CONVERSATIONAL ANALYSIS (see Appendix)

In order to illustrate the theory discussed above, I would like to take some conversations as examples to analyze in terms of turn-taking signals. The conversations are extracted from the book “101 helpful hints for IELTS” by Adams, G. and Peck, T. (2006). The conversations are both in words and voice recorded, therefore, it is quite clear to analyze the signals. However, because of the small scope of this project, I would like to focus my analysis on three types of all the signals: the use of linguistic signals, intonation and pauses which frequently occur in the conversations.

3.1 Analysis of verbal signals

One of the most outstanding results found in the conversations is that the verbal signals are used the most frequently of the total turns. In particular, the use of questions-answer and complete sentence is the most significant to realise turns. For example:

- E: Oh, hi, Jon. Yes, it didn't take long. What about you?
- J: Oh, because I've re-enrolled for another year, I don't have to be here until this afternoon, but I thought I'd come along and help
- E: Oh, that's very kind of you, Jon. Maybe you could help me with this elective class timetable. It's for students who need more English practice, like me
- J: Yeah, it's a good idea.
- J: OH, I see. Well, what do you need?
- E: I need everything, (+) but especially writing practice
- J: I'm afraid so. How's your reading, Ewa?
- E: Oh, I'm a bit slow. Yes, I think I will study Writing, Reading and Grammar in the morning...
- J: //and Listening and Vocabulary in the afternoon. Good choice! Now what do you have to do?//
- E: Umm (+) just give this form to my tutor tomorrow.
- J: Do you have any classes today?
- E: There's a special introductory English class for foreign students later this morning.
- J: What time's the class?
- E: We have to be at the function room at 11.00 a.m.
- J: I'm already a member of the Table Tennis Club and the Orienteering Club. Do you want to play table tennis?
- E: I'm not much good, I'm afraid. What else is there?
- J: Fencing, tennis, hang-gliding ...

E: What about orienteering? How much is it to join?

J: For second year student, it's cheaper. Only £10 (+), but for first year, it's £2, I think.
Do you want to become a member?

Bearing in mind that, answers are needed after questions; the listeners in these examples quickly get their turns so that the conversations move smoothly without any misunderstanding or silence. Furthermore, the use of complete sentence or information is also effective here.

3.2 Analysis of intonation

Intonation is also used much frequently in the conversations. However, it can be interpreted differently depending on particular situations. As mentioned previously, English intonation includes several elements of which tone is considered to contribute to a wide range of different meanings. This part just focuses on the use of Rises and Falls of tone.

First of all, using Rises within a turn is an effective way to hold one's turn; to show that the speaker is speaking and there is still something to say next. For example:

3. J: Oh, because I've re-enrolled for another year, you know? ↑ So I don't have to be here until this afternoon, but I thought I'd come along and help.

36. J: This is my second year. I started (+) er (+) well, one year ago. Tell me again. ↑ What is it that you're studying? Computing, isn't it? Basic Programing?

82. C: 0 1 2 2 2 5 6 5 2 4 8. Er (+) now all you have to do is to pay the £15 ↑ and I'll fix you up with a Club Membership card. Here's an information sheet about the Club. See you later.

In order to hold his turn, Jon (turn 3, 36) raises his voice within his utterances showing that he will continue his turns with some more information, and that his information sharing has not finished. In turn 82, the Clerk also uses the rise tone to indicate that his turn still continues.

In addition, rise tone at the end of a statement or a Yes/No question can be interpreted as a signal to yield turn and take turn. In the extracted conversations, this Rise tone occurs so many times with the same meaning. For example:

11. J: Ok, so Grammar and Writing Skills in the afternoon? ↑

20. E: Do I have to take Grammar? ↑

54. C: Family name? ↑

68. C: When we climb we always nominate a partner; it's good for teamwork, and you both look out for each other? ↑

75. J: Is Sunday morning good for you, Ewa? ↑

The Rise tone in these examples is used as a signal to pass the turn. The speakers here all raise their voices at the end of the statement or sentence to turn over the floor; their expectation from the Rise tone is an answer from the listener.

Apart from the Rise tone, the use of Fall tone is also employed as an indicator to pass the turn in conversation. For example:

4. E: Oh, that's very kind of you, Jon. Maybe you could help me with this elective class timetable. It's for students who need more English practice, like me. ↓
8. E: I need everything, (+) but especially writing practice ↓
19. J: Then your best choice would be to study Listening and Vocabulary in the afternoon, and Writing, Reading and Grammar in the morning. ↓
28. E: There's a special introductory English class for foreign students later this morning. ↓

3.3 Analysis of pause/silence

Pause is the signal used very often in the conversations. It can not be denied that pausing can also be seen as a strategic pattern in conversation if all the floor-holders know how to use it and realizes its implied meanings in certain cases. Basically, pauses are used for all purposes such as to keep turn, to take turn and to yield turn. Pauses are very effective in formulating the ideas to express and keeping turns. Therefore, pauses are unavoidable in conversation. As mentioned above there are two types of pauses switching pause and hesitation pause which are used to hold turn and take turn. However, in the extracted conversations, only hesitation pause is used in order to hold turn. For example:

8. E: I need everything, (+) but especially writing practice.
18. J: WELL, in that case, Reading and Writing in the morning, followed by Pronunciation (+) uhm, then Listening and Speaking in the afternoon.
21. J: Er (+), well, if you want to improve your writing
22. E: Yes, I suppose you're right. And (+) uhm (+) er (+) Writing class first lesson in the morning?
66. C: Next thing is (+) do you know your blood type? Umh (+) just for safety reasons.

To hold turns, pauses are also used in combination with some discourse markers like "but, so, umm, well, uh..." or even after a rise tone. In turn 18 and 22, Jon and Ewa use the discourse markers "uhm; er" together with a short pause in order to hold their turns. In turn 21, Jon uses "er, well" with a short pause to take a new turn.

By using pauses, the speakers all express their hesitation as a communication strategy. It is clear that they use pauses very frequently and this may lead the conversation.

4 CONCLUSION

Turn taking mechanism is the way in which speakers hold or pass the floor, it varies between cultures and languages and it is the most obvious characteristics of conversation. The writing has dealt with the basic concepts of turn as well as turn-taking in conversation. Moreover, signals in turn-taking and the analysis of certain signals is also presented thoroughly both in theory and practice.

By doing this assignment, I really had a chance to widen my knowledge; to have an overview of the subject matter, however, because of limited time and knowledge as well as the small scope of the assignment, errors are unavoidable. I do hope to receive precious comments from the concerned readers.

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APPENDIX

Convention of the transcription

//.....//	overlap
(+)	pause of less than two seconds
[...]	silence
WELL	indication of increased volume
<.....>	indication of decreased volume
↑↓	raised or lowered intonation

The extracted conversations

(1) Ewa is an overseas student who has just enrolled at the National Business College. Her friend, Jon, meets her on enrolment day.

E: Ewa J: Jon

1. J: Hi, Ewa. I SEE you've just enrolled. ↓
2. E: Oh, hi, Jon. Yes, it didn't take long. What about you? ↑
3. J: Oh, because I've re-enrolled for another year, you know? ↑ So I don't have to be here until this afternoon, but I thought I'd come along and help. ↓
4. E: Oh, that's very kind of you, Jon. Maybe you could help me with this elective class timetable. It's for students who need more English practice, like me. ↓
5. J: Yeah, it's a good idea.

6. E: It's on Friday and I have to choose which timetable is best for me. There are four to choose from. Here, take a look.
7. J: OH, I see. Well, what do you need?
8. E: I need everything, (+) but especially writing practice. ↓
9. J: Well, do you want to go to the Writing Skills in the morning or the afternoon? ↓
10. E: In the afternoon, I think ↓
11. J: //Ok, so Grammar and Writing Skills in the afternoon? ↑ //
12. E: Grammar? Oh, no. I don't want to study grammar.
13. J: WELL, in that case, Reading and Writing in the morning, ↑ followed by Pronunciation (+) uhm, then Listening and Speaking in the afternoon.
14. E: I don't think my pronunciation is too bad, do you?
15. J: No, no, you speak very clearly. ↓
16. E: Yes, but I do need more vocabulary.
17. J: If you study Vocabulary in the morning, you have to study Grammar in the afternoon. What about Listening? ↑
18. E: Oh, yes. I certainly need to practice <more listening> ↓
19. J1: Then your best choice would be to study Listening and Vocabulary in the afternoon, and Writing, Reading and Grammar in the morning. ↓
20. E: Do I have to take Grammar?
21. J: Er, well, if you want to improve your writing.
22. E: Yes, I suppose you're right. And (+) um (+) er (+) Writing class first lesson in the morning? ↓
23. J: I'm afraid so. How's your reading, Ewa?
24. E: Oh, I'm a bit slow. Yes, I think I will study Writing, Reading and Grammar in the morning...
25. J: //and Listening and Vocabulary in the afternoon. Good choice! Now what do you have to do?//
26. E: Umm (+) just give this form to my tutor tomorrow.
27. J: Do you have any classes today?
28. E: There's a special introductory English class for foreign students later this morning. ↓
29. J: What time's the class?
30. E: We have to be at the function room at 11.00 a.m.
31. J: It's five past nine now.
32. E: //it's actually nine thirty//
33. J: Oh, right. We've got time, so why don't I take you down to the Student Centre?

34. E: OK.

(2) Jon and Ewa continue their conversation in the Student Centre.

35. E: Jon, how many years have you been studying at the College? ↑

36. J: This is my second year. I started (+) er (+) well, one year ago. Tell me again. What is it that you're studying? ↑ Computing, isn't it? ↑ Basic Programming?

37. E: Yes, I worked as a computer programmer after I graduated from university.

38. J: So why are you doing Basic Programming?

39. E: No, no. Advanced Programming.

40. J: Right. Well, here we're at the Student Centre.

41. E: Oh, it's huge. ↓

42. J: Yeah, well, it has to be. There are 500 students on campus and 50 staffs.

43. E: Oh, look, there's some information about clubs.

44. J: I'm already a member of the Table Tennis Club and the Orienteering Club.
Do you want to play table tennis?

45. E: I'm not much good, I'm afraid. What else is there? ↓

46. J: Fencing, tennis, hang-gliding ... ↑

47. E: What about orienteering? How much is it to join? ↑

48. J: For second year student, it's cheaper. Only £10 (+), but for first year, it's £2, I think.
Do you want to become a member?

49. E: Why not?

50. J: OK, let's go to the Student Information Office. Over here...

(3) At the Student Information Office, Ewa wants to join the Orienteering Club. She has to give information about herself to the clerk.

J: Jon

E: Ewa

C: Clerk

51. J: Hello. ↓ My friend, Ewa is a new student ↑ and she would like to join the Orienteering Club.

52. C: No problem. All I have to do is to fill in this registration form, and the cost is only £15 for first year students. To start with, I need your fullname. Ewa, isn't it?

53. E: Yes, E-W-A.

54. C: Family name? ↑

55. E: Zaleska

56. C: Zaleska (+) umh (+) how do you spell that?

57. E: Z-A-L-E-S-K-A.

58. C: Za-les-ka. Very good. And you're from (+)? ↑

59. E: Poland.
60. C: Nationality: Polish. I went to Poland last year. Great place. OK, so what's your student number?
61. J: (+) Er (+) on your student card.
62. E: Oh, right. Here it is: 3 4 9 6 8 – A P
63. C: 3 4 9 6 8- A P. Got it. You must be doing the Advanced Programing course. Tell me about your orienteering experience? ↑ How long have you been doing it?
64. E: Two years.
65. J: //You're probably better than I am// ↓
66. C: Next thing is (+) do you know your blood type? Umh (+) just for satety reasons...
67. E: Oh, right. Yes, it is A positive.
68. C: When we climb we always nominate a partner; it's good for teamwork, and you both look out for each other? ↑
69. J: OK, we'll be partners.
70. C: Right. So what's your name?
71. J: Jon. J-O-N.
72. C: Family name? ↑
73. J: Anderburg. A-N-D-E-R-B-U-R-G.
74. C: Good, when would you like to climb?
75. J: Is Sunday morning good for you, Ewa?
76. E: Not really, Jon. I go to church.
77. C: We have sessions this afternoon, too. Only on weekends, though.
78. E: Oh, well, Saturday afternoon. Is it OK for you?
79. J: Sure. ↑
80. C: Saturday PM. One more thing, I need a contact number if we need to ring you (+) change in the weather or something like that (+) er (+) your homephone number? ↑
81. E: 0 1 2 2 2 5 6 5 2 4 8
82. C: 0 1 2 2 2 5 6 5 2 4 8. Er (+) now all you have to do is to pay the £15 and I'll fix you up with a Club Membership card. Here's an information sheet about the Club. See you later.
83. J: Bye. Hey, Ewa, we've still got plenty of time, let's watch some TV. ↑
84. E: All right.